

Eco-friendly synthesis of condensed nitrogen heterocycles : A brief experience from our group[†]

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Manuscript received 05 July 2013, accepted 06 July 2013

Abstract : In order to develop eco-friendly syntheses of condensed nitrogen heterocycles, solvent-free syntheses on solid acidic catalysts and aqueous reactions using a phase transfer catalyst (PTC) were successfully carried out. The catalysts used were (i) TLC-grade silica gel G (SiO₂), (ii) SiO₂ doped with 10 mol% phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄-SiO₂), (iii) Montmorillonite K10 clay (K10), (iv) acid-washed K10 clay (acid-clay), (v) K10 doped with one equivalent (with respect to substrate) of tosic acid (TsOH-K10) and (vi) cetylpyridinium bromide (CPB) (5 mol%) as the PTC. The reactions were carried out at room temperature (rt), at 60–70 °C (oven) or under microwave irradiation (MWI).

Keywords : Heterocycles, eco-friendly synthesis, solvent-free, aqueous, green catalysts.

Introduction

During the last decade, we worked on the synthesis and reactions of condensed nitrogen heterocycles since heterocyclic compounds play a major and significant role in our everyday life^{1a}. In the early twentieth century, a chemist with foresight, G. Ciamician observed that the then extant syntheses of compounds related to natural products required harsh conditions and excess energy. He commented that actual advancement in synthetic chemistry would mean to be able to synthesise compounds in a mild way as nature does. He meant development of environment-friendly chemistry^{1b-c}. Decades later, the growing conflict between the ever increasing pollution of environment by the industries on one hand and the undeniable need to develop industries, specially chemical industries, on the other hand led IUPAC to float the philosophy of “Sustainable Chemistry” whose objective was to develop ways and means of pursuing chemistry in an environment-friendly manner². Paul Anastas, a Member of a related IUPAC Committee, coined the term “Green Chemistry” which was defined as the “invention, design and application of chemical products and processes to

reduce or to eliminate the use and generation of hazardous substances³.

In our work, we resorted to the following out of the twelve principles of Green Chemistry⁴ : (i) the use of harmless acidic, basic and neutral solids with large surface areas as catalysts, (ii) the carrying out of reactions in a solvent-free manner and in water and (iii) the use of an alternative non-conventional source of energy, viz. microwave (MW).

The catalysts that we employed are Montmorillonite K10 clay (K10), named after Montmorillon of France and perhaps the most widely explored catalyst in solvent-free reactions⁵, silica gel G (TLC-grade; SiO₂), neutral alumina and a phase transfer catalyst (PTC; in reactions in water). Whenever a more acidic catalyst was necessitated, we used acid-washed K10 clay (designated “acid-clay”), K10 clay doped with tosic acid (TsOH-K10) and silica gel G doped with phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄-SiO₂). The required concentrations of tosic acid and phosphoric acid were determined by trial experiments.

In our so called solvent-free reactions, the reactants were dissolved in required minimum of solvents, adsorbed

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

on the solid catalyst and the solvent allowed to evaporate off at room temperature (rt). Also, solvents had to be used to leach the product(s) from the solid matrix. In defence, we like to reiterate what Professor Koichi Tanaka, Nobel Laureate, of Ehime University, Japan stated : the use of solvents for the two aforesaid purposes are not counted in the field of solvent-free organic synthesis⁶.

We used a domestic MW oven (BPL Sanyo; 50% power, i.e. 400 Watt) whenever the reactions failed or proved to be extremely sluggish at rt or even at 60–70 °C (oven).

To note, the various classes of compounds that we synthesised had earlier been prepared but in solution phase using conditions contrary to the principles of green chemistry. Moreover, often the reactions required long periods, the yields were extremely low or of a wide range, the starting materials had to be prepared by multi-step syntheses and the isolation of pure products involved tedious separation procedures. This situation motivated us to develop solvent-free or aqueous syntheses using environmentally benign catalysts since we could not take resort to an established alternative, viz. Mechanochemistry⁷ which requires the use of expensive ball mills that we could not afford.

For the sake of brevity, we have presented herein only that part of our work which involved the use of K10 clay, TsOH-K10, SiO₂, H₃PO₄-SiO₂ and a PTC. The references too have been restricted to the bare minimum. In most of the cases, we checked the recyclability of catalysts at least up to the second cycle.

Identification of products

All new compounds were crystallised, purity checked by TLC on silica gel G (Merck) and identified by FT IR, ¹H (500 MHz) and ¹³C (PND, DEPT-135) NMR, LR and HR EI-MS spectroscopic and elemental analyses. The individual ¹H and ¹³C NMR assignments of a representative member of all classes of compounds and critically important compounds were ascertained from their HMQC and HMBC spectra. In a few cases, the spectroscopically derived structures were confirmed by single crystal XRD analysis.

Actual work

Synthesis of bis(indolyl)ethylamines (BIEAs) on K10 clay :

Our work in the domain of green synthesis began with

BIEAs as target molecules, which was triggered by the reported isolation of three BIEAs from marine fauna in the 1990s^{8,9} (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Naturally occurring BIEAs.

Since the two previous general synthesis of BIEAs^{10–12} were carried out in solution, we developed a solvent-free general synthesis of bis(indolyl)nitroethanes (BINEs) which were expected to be reducible to BIEAs. 3-Unsubstituted indoles (**1**) were treated with one equivalent of 3-(2'-nitrovinyl)indole (**2**)¹³, a well known Michael receptor, on TLC-grade silica gel in a solvent-free manner both at rt and under MWI, which efficiently furnished the BINEs (**3**) (Scheme 1)^{14,15}.

The reaction failed, as apprehended, in the cases of *N*-acetylindole, skatole and 1,3-dimethylindole.

A host of common reductants, viz. LiAlH₄, NiCl₂·6H₂O/NaBH₄, Zn/HCl, H₂/Pd-C (1 atm), Ni₂B/NH₂NH₂·H₂O and In/NH₄Cl were employed to reduce the BINEs to the corresponding BIEAs, but to no avail. Finally, ammonium formate-palladised charcoal^{16,17} became successful with BINE itself, and the resulting BIEA was isolated as its acetamide (**4**) (Scheme 2).

Synthesis of diindolylalkanes (DIAs) on K10 clay :

Our next target compounds were DIAs, also known as bis(indolyl)alkanes (BIAs), whose reported syntheses, all in solution phase, and bioactivities had previously been

Scheme 1. Solvent-free synthesis of BINEs on SiO₂.

Scheme 2. Reduction of BINE to *N*-Ac-BIEA (4).

reviewed by us¹⁸. The DIAs were important because (i) four members, viz. 5-8 were natural products¹⁹⁻²² (Fig. 2), (ii) one of these, viz. vibrindole A (7) had been synthesised at least thrice even before its isolation from a natural source and (iii) diindolylmethane (DIM) (R = R' = H), a product of acid-catalysed dimerisation (in stomach) of indole-3-carbinol occurring as its glucosinolate in the cruciferous vegetables cabbage and broccoli, induces apoptosis in cancer cells²³⁻²⁵. DIM, also known as arundine, had previously been isolated from plant²⁵ as

Fig. 2. Naturally occurring DIAs.

well as from the marine bacteria *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*^{21b}.

We developed a solvent-free, general synthesis of DIAs (10) by the reaction of 3-unsubstituted indoles (1a, b, g) (2 equiv.) with (hetero)arylaldehydes, acyclic and cyclic ketones and 2-formylheteroarenes (9) on K10 clay²⁶ (Scheme 3).

The reactions with ketones were comparatively sluggish, furnishing the DIAs in lower yields.

We also prepared the naturally occurring DIAs (5-8) by this method (Scheme 4).

Interestingly, while the reaction of indole (3 equiv.) with each of 2-formylthiophene and furfural furnished the expected DIAs smoothly, a similar reaction with 2-formylpyrrole afforded symmetrical tris(3-indolyl)methane (TIM) as the only product (Scheme 5). A plausible mechanism of the formation of the latter is shown.

TIM and vibrindole A (7) are *Vibrio* metabolites^{21b}, which renders our present undesigned synthesis of TIM useful.

The reaction of skatole with each of 2- and 3-nitrobenzaldehydes furnished a mixture of the respective 2,2'-DIA (11/13) and the 2,3'-DIA (12/14) (Scheme 6). The products resulted from the initially formed bis-(azafulvenium) salts, followed by three appropriate

Scheme 3. Solvent-free synthesis of DIAs (10) on K10 clay.

Scheme 4. Solvent-free synthesis of 5-8 on K10 clay.

Scheme 5. Solvent-free reaction of indole with 2-formylheteroarenes on K10 clay.

Scheme 6. Formation of two types of DIAs on K10 clay.

Plancher rearrangements^{27,28a,b} (not shown here). This is the first report of the formation of 2,3'-DIAs from a 3-alkylindole.

Synthesis of TIMs on K10 clay :

As a logical extension of this piece of work, a solvent-free synthesis of symmetrical TIMs was attempted by us by treating indole and its *N*-methyl/ethyl derivatives (3 equiv.) with 3-formylindole (3-FI) on K10 clay. While indole furnished only TIM itself, each of *N*-methyl and *N*-ethylindoles afforded a mixture of the corresponding symmetrical TIM and two types of unsymmetrical TIMs, viz. **15b/c** and **16b/c** (Scheme 7)²⁹. Clearly, the products resulted from the initially formed, unisolable bis(indolyl)carbinols by tandem addition-elimination-Michael addition reactions (mechanism not shown here).

Skatole (**1i**) furnished symmetrical tris(3-methyl-2-

indolyl)methane along with an unsymmetrical TIM whereas each of 2-methylindole (**1f**), 1,2-dimethylindole (**1h**) and 1,3-dimethylindole (**1j**) formed only one type of unsymmetrical TIM (**17f**, **h** and **j**, respectively) (Scheme 8). 2,3-Dimethylindole simply failed to react, as anticipated.

Our work assumed importance in view of the reported isolation of, *inter alia*, 1,1,1-tris(3'-indolyl)ethane from the solvent extracts of indole-supplemented supernatants of *E. coli* and *Corynebacteria* (*Brevibacterium flavum*)²².

Synthesis of naturally occurring DIAs on K10 clay :

We next explored the efficacy of SiO₂ itself to bring about the reaction between 3-unsubstituted indoles and araldehydes in a solvent-free manner. SiO₂ proved not to be acidic enough. But, when doped with H₃PO₄ (10 mol%), the resulting catalyst (H₃PO₄-SiO₂), a free-flowing solid, furnished the symmetrical DIAs (**18**) efficiently (Scheme 9)³⁰.

Scheme 7. Synthesis of symmetrical and unsymmetrical TIMs on K10 clay.

Scheme 8. Reaction of indoles 1f, h, j with 3-FI on K10 clay.

Scheme 9. Synthesis of DIAs on H₃PO₄-SiO₂.

Like K10 clay, this reagent (H₃PO₄-SiO₂) too was successfully applied to the solvent-free synthesis of the three *Vibrio* metabolites vibrindole A (7)^{21a,b}, TIM^{21b} and trisindoline (19)^{21b,31} (Scheme 10).

Alternate synthesis of only symmetrical TIMs on "acid-clay" :

We next tried to develop an alternate synthesis of only symmetrical TIMs specially because of their importance

Scheme 10. Synthesis of *Vibrio* metabolites on H₃PO₄-SiO₂.

in physicochemical research and dye industry and because of the isolation of two symmetrical TIMs, depicted below (Fig. 3), from natural sources.

Fig. 3. Naturally occurring symmetrical TIMs.

For the synthesis of TIM itself, the reaction of indole (3 equiv.) with triethyl orthoformate (TEOF) was tried at rt and also under MWI using K10 clay as the catalyst. A monitoring of the reaction course by TLC showed that TIM was being formed, but the reaction was extremely sluggish under both the conditions. We, therefore, tried acid-washed K10 clay (c. HCl, 4 d; filtered, washed with water, aq. EtOH, vacuum dried, 110 °C/oven, 8 h) since the washing of this clay with mineral acids was reported to increase its acidity sharply (Hammett acidity function H₀: -6 to -8)⁵. The resulting free-flowing solid, which we designated “acid-clay”, was used as the catalyst.

When 3-unsubstituted indoles (3 equiv.) were treated with TEOF on “acid-clay” at rt in a solvent-free manner, the corresponding symmetrical TIMs were formed efficiently (Scheme 11)³³.

Scheme 11. Solvent-free synthesis of symmetrical TIMs on “acid-clay”.

Scheme 12. Reaction of 3-methylindoles with TEOF on “acid-clay”.

Skatole (**1i**) expectedly furnished tris(3-methyl-2-indolyl)methane (**21**) whereas 1,3-dimethylindole (**1j**) afforded both the corresponding symmetrical TIM (**22**) and the 2-formylindole (**23**) arising via the unisolable acetal, followed by its *in situ* hydrolysis (Scheme 12).

5-Bromoindole (**1g**) behaved differently, quickly furnishing the corresponding symmetrical TIM (**24**) and the *N*-formyl unsymmetrical TIM (**25**) as the products (Scheme 13). The mechanism of formation of the novel product **25** is also shown in the Scheme.

The structure of **25**, since rather unusual, was additionally confirmed by single crystal XRD analysis (ORTEP diagram of **25**.CH₂Cl₂ (1 : 1) in Fig. 4).

The used “acid-clay” was found to be recyclable at least up to the second cycle. The present work constitutes the first general solvent-free synthesis of only symmetrical TIMs.

Synthesis of 2-substituted thiazolo[4,5-c]carbazoles on K10 and TsOH-K10 :

We had earlier prepared the target molecules in solution³⁴. We, therefore, developed a solvent-free, regio-selective synthesis of only one type of thiazolocarbazoles, viz. the target compounds, which was lacking in literature.

In our method, a number of 3-aminocarbazoles (**26**), with or without substitution at C-2, were condensed with alkyl and aryl isothiocyanates (1 equiv.) on K10 clay at rt

Fig. 4. ORTEP diagram of **25**.

in a solvent-free manner when the corresponding 3-(*N'*-alkyl/aryl)thioureidocarbazoles (**27**) were quickly formed in high yields. When kept adsorbed on K10 clay doped with tosic acid (TsOH; 1 equiv. w.r.t. substrate) at 60–70 °C, these intermediates cyclised regioselectively to 2-(alkyl/aryl)aminothiazolo[4,5-*c*]carbazoles (**28**) (Scheme 14)³⁵.

Rather unexpectedly, 3-(*N'*-methyl)thioureidocarbazoles **29** could not be prepared by the K10 clay-mediated method. These were, therefore, prepared from the corresponding 3-aminocarbazoles and methyl isothiocyanate by our previously reported solution-phase synthesis (MeOH, reflux)³⁴ and then cyclised by TsOH-K10

in a solvent-free manner to furnish similar angular thiazolocarbazoles (Scheme 14).

Pertinently, this was the first general solvent-free, regioselective synthesis of this class of thiazolocarbazoles.

Synthesis of 3,3-bis(indolyl)-2-indolones on K10 clay :

Yet another usefulness of K10 clay was in the field of 3,3-bis(indolyl)-2-indolones, of which trisindoline (**19**) is a natural product^{21b,31}. Indeed, the reports on the occurrence of **19** and a high yield of indole in the same marine *Vibrio* sp.^{21b,31} and of isatin (**30a**) in another marine invertebrate, an *Altermonas* sp.³⁶, led to a suggestion that **19** may have been formed abiotically from indole and isatin, as shown in Scheme 15.

We utilised this clue to study the reaction of 3-unsubstituted indoles (3-equiv., needed to expedite the reactions) with isatin on K10 clay at rt in a solvent-free manner, which furnished the 3,3-bis(3'-indolyl)-2-indolones (**31**) efficiently (Scheme 16)³⁷.

Interestingly, skatole furnished the expected bis(2'-skatolyl)-2-indolone (**32**) along with a minor product (**33**) which had earlier been proven by us^{38a} to be the clay-catalysed autoxidation product of skatole itself. Prior to our work, **33** had been prepared from skatole by *N*-chlorosuccinimide (NCS)^{38b}. Our work is presented in Scheme 17.

5-Nitroisatin (**30b**) furnished with indole the expected bis(3'-indolyl)-2-indolone (**34**) along with 3-hydroxy-3-

Scheme 14. Synthesis of thiazolo[4,5-*c*]carbazoles on TsOH-K10 clay.

Scheme 15. Suggested abiotic formation of 19.

Scheme 16. Solvent-free synthesis of 31 on K10 clay.

Scheme 17. Solvent-free reaction of skatole with isatin on K10 clay.

(3'-indolyl)-2-indolone (**35**), thereby suggesting the formation of the former from the initially formed **35** (Scheme 18).

thyl-*o*-PD (**36** : R = Me) reacted with equivalent amounts of each of anisaldehyde, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and 3-formylindole under similar conditions to result in the for-

Scheme 18. Solvent-free reaction of **30b** with indole on K10 clay.

Formation of benzimidazoles on $TsOH-SiO_2$:

We next harped on benzimidazoles because many such compounds are used as anthelmintics in veterinary medicine^{39,40} and have therapeutic potential for human beings too⁴¹.

Our objective was to avoid the harsh conditions that are employed for the oxidative cyclisation of *o*-phenylenediamines (*o*-PDs) with araldehydes or their masked forms in solution for the extant synthetic routes to benzimidazoles. We used silica gel G doped with 5 mol% tosic acid ($TsOH-SiO_2$) to efficiently bring about the desired reaction of *o*-PD itself (**36a** : R = H) with a variety of (hetero)aryl aldehydes (2 equiv.) in a solvent-free manner at 60–70 °C. As a result, a mixture of 2-aryl (**37**) and 2-aryl-1-arylmethylbenzimidazoles (**38**) were formed in excellent overall yields (Scheme 19)⁴².

Curiously, 4-cyano- and 3-nitrobenzaldehydes as well

mation of only 2-(hetero)aryl-*N*(1)-methylbenzimidazoles (**37** : R = Me; Ar = 4-OMe/ $NO_2C_6H_4$, 3-indolyl; 82/87/81%; 10/5/10 min).

The advantages of this procedure are that it is a solvent-free reaction, fast and efficient and the reagent is cheap and environmentally benign too.

Synthesis of benzimidazoles in water using a PTC :

In view of the importance of aqueous reactions in green chemistry^{43a,b} and the avoidance of waste generation by PTCs^{44a-c}, we developed another green synthesis of 1-substituted 2-arylbenzimidazoles from *N*-alkyl/aryl-*o*-PDs and araldehydes in water using the PTC, CPB (5 mol%). The latter proved to be superior to four other PTCs, viz. TBAB, CTAB, BTAC and TBAHS tried towards this end. The yields were very good to excellent, although the reactions could be expedited by using higher concentrations of CPB. The work is presented in Scheme 20⁴⁵.

Scheme 19. Solvent-free reaction of *o*-PD with araldehydes on $TsOH-SiO_2$.

as 3-FI furnished only 1,2-disubstituted products (**38** : 84/78/76%) in 10–15 min whereas 4-nitrobenzaldehyde afforded only the 2-aryl product (**37** : 87%) in 5 min.

Clearly, the method could be utilised to selectively synthesise only the 2-aryl-*N*(1)-alkyl/arylbenzimidazoles by using *N*-alkyl/aryl-*o*-PD as a reactant. Indeed, *N*-me-

CPB, acting like a surfactant, increases the substrate concentration at air-water interface, thereby causing aerial oxidation of the initially formed unisolable substituted benzimidazolines, leading to the formation of **37** as the only isolated products (Scheme 21).

Prior to our work, four reports appeared on the aque-

Scheme 20. PTC-mediated aqueous synthesis of benzimidazoles.

Scheme 21. Role of CPB in the formation of 37 in water.

ous synthesis – two only on 2-aryl-1-arylmethylbenzimidazoles using Zn-proline-H₂O⁴⁶ and SiO₂-H₂SO₄-LiCl-H₂O⁴⁷ and two only on 2-arylbenzimidazoles using H₂O₂-HCl-LiCl-H₂O⁴⁸ and I₂-KI-K₂CO₃-H₂O⁴⁹. Of these, ours and the last named method are environmentally benign.

Attempted Knoevenagel condensation of ninhydrin on K10 clay :

Ninhydrin (**38**) is a molecule with unique carbonyl character. We were curious to check its behavior with various active methylene compounds when K10 clay is used as the catalyst and the reactions are carried out in a solvent-free manner. To our surprise, the results were quite diverse.

Thus, with **38**, malononitrile, a highly reactive methylene compound, furnished the expected Knoevenagel condensate (**39**), whereas six other active methylene compounds formed only the corresponding aldols (**40**) and indane-1,3-dione afforded only trisindanedione (**41**), a product of tandem Knoevenagel condensation-Michael addition (Scheme 22)⁵⁰.

The product **41**, reported to be bioactive⁵¹, had earlier been prepared by electrolysis of 2,2-dibromoindane-1,3-dione using a graphite cathode⁵². Since the melting point of **41** was not reported in these two papers, we additionally confirmed its structure by direct comparison with a sample prepared by us from **38** and indane-1,3-dione by treatment with acetic acid (rt, 2 h; 86%), followed by tandem dehydration-Michael addition of the resulting aldol with indane-1,3-dione in HOAc-conc. H₂SO₄ (rt, 5 h; 65%), following a reported procedure⁵³.

Further, **38** resulted in the formation of a decarboxylated (at rt) aldol (**42**) from its reaction with malonic acid, dihydroxydihydrofuroindanones (**43a-c**), formed via

Scheme 22. Attempted Knoevenagel condensation of 38 on K10 clay.

aldols by tandem hemi-ketalisation-enolisation-heteroannulation, from three 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and a mechanistically interesting 2,2-disubstituted indane-1,3-dione (**44**) resulting from Meldrum's acid (MA) (Scheme 23)⁵⁰.

separately, the catalyst was found to be recyclable at least up to the second cycle albeit with somewhat lower efficiency.

Further, when a suspension of **38** and some of the active methylene compounds, stated above, in water were

Scheme 23. Attempted Knoevenagel condensations of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds on K10 clay (rt, 5 min).

The structures of both **42** and **44** were also confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis (ORTEP diagram of **42** : Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. ORTEP diagram of **42**.

Cyanoacetamide, hydantoin and thiazoline-2,4-dione failed to react with **38** under similar conditions and even at 60–70 °C. Using the reactions of **38** with ethyl cyanoacetate, cyclohexane-1,3-dione and acetylacetone

separately heated on a steam-bath, similar products were isolated in most cases in 83–98% yields. As exceptions, indane-1,3-dione furnished the corresponding diol nearly quantitatively, and MA led to the isolation of the decarboxylated **42** (93%) as against the formation of the corresponding methyl ester **44** from the corresponding clay-catalysed reaction.

Conclusion

The architecture of Green Synthesis is based on three pillars – green catalysts (homogeneous, heterogeneous and supported (nano)catalysts), reaction media (solvent-free, water and ionic liquids) and alternative, non-conventional sources of energy (microwave, photochemistry, ultrasound and electrochemistry)⁵⁴. In our research pursuit, we have used one or more of all the three components. Due to the well documented efficacy of synergy between dry media and microwave irradiation⁵⁵, we have also utilised this combination. More than half of our work has been briefly covered in this article, which spanned over a decade and resulted in ten publications. The suc-

cess and diversity of the results reaffirm the enormous potential of Green Synthesis. It was indeed a rewarding exercise.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authority of Bose Institute for providing laboratory facilities and to the CSIR, Government of India, for providing financial assistance in the form of Emeritus Scientistship (MC) and Fellowships (the research scholars).

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